

THE PLACE OF THE GREAT SINGER IN THE ART OF NATIONAL SINGING

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Abstract: This article tells about the factors of revival and development of the genre of maqom in the art of Uzbek folk music performance and the work currently being done in our country to develop the art of maqom.

Keywords: Music, status, melody, song, instrument, performance, challenge, conference.

Restoration and development of the maqom genre in the art of musical performance. In the 17th-19th centuries, no major works were created with detailed descriptions of instruments. This is more due to the intensification of feudal fragmentation. The huge state was divided into separate khanates. (Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand khanates). This was reflected in the development of musical art. Uzbek musical culture began to acquire local characteristics. Unique musical instruments were formed. From now on, maqoms, among the types of music, were improved in their own direction in each khanate. Maqom performers made changes as necessary. Despite this, they retained the general characteristics of the music. Each performer creatively approached the performance of maqoms and introduced unique, unique aspects to the performance of music. The tradition of preserving musical instruments orally is one of the main features of the maqom, without which it is difficult to imagine its survival and further development. In each khanate, new types of folk music were created in a specific direction; festive, melodious, folk show tunes (dorbozlik, koghurchokbozlik), new types of dance tunes. These tunes were distinguished by their cheerfulness and cheerfulness and attracted a wide audience. At the end of the 17th and beginning of the 19th centuries, many new types of folk and professional musical art began to develop in Uzbek musical culture: katta ashula, katta oyn, Shodiyona, Navruz, Mavrigiy, Shashmaqom, Chor maqom (which included Dugoh, Husayniy, Chorgoh, Bayot, Gulyori-Shahnoz). Depending on the musical instruments and performers available in the locality, various instrumental ensembles were formed. In most cases, the folk instrument ensemble included musical instruments such as gijjak, tanbur, dutar, chang, nay, koshnay, doira. Shashmaqom, consisting of six series of works, was especially popular in music. It arose as a result of the long development of professional music of the peoples of Central Asia in the form of a suite (series). I. Rajabov writes: Shashmaqom consists of six different systems, each of which, in turn, is divided into the following maqams (parts), consisting of mushkilot (instrument) and prose (song) sections: "Rost", "Buzrug", "Navo", "Dugoh", "Segoh", "Iraq" ... Each maqam includes from 20 to 40 large and small parts. In total, there are about 250 mushkilot and prose parts in the series. The performance of one maqam lasted several hours. Folk instruments develop in close connection with folk oral art and classical literature. The ideas about folk instruments are enriched by the representations of musical instruments in works of art, the images of musicians in book miniatures. The works of Firdawsi, Saadi, Navoi, Dehlavi mention the names of more than 60 folk instruments. Maqoms were mainly performed in the presence of courtiers at certain times or under certain conditions.

It is known that a kind of competition of skilled singers was even organized (especially in performing climaxes, as well as in pouring out new parts). The revival and development of the maqom genre in the art of musical performance continued. According to its laws of melody and rhythm, the maqom was inextricably linked with folk songs, differing only in the breadth of its scope. Usually, each maqom was divided into two large parts. The first - the part performed only on instruments - was called mushkilot, the second - the part sung to the accompaniment of instruments - was called prosr. Prosr also included dance music. Among the musicians, there was a desire to create a notation, a system of special symbols that would indicate the sounds of music. The poet-musician Pahlavan Niyoz Mirzabashi (Komil Khorezmi 1825-1879) was credited with implementing this. A talented musician, a skilled tanbur player and gijjak player, Pahlavan Niyoz Mirzabashi, was amazed when he saw musicians playing according to the notes during his travels. Mirzabashi - Komil Khorezmi immediately began to write down the maqoms, an intention that had been in his heart for a long time. Muhammad Yaqub Kharratov (1867-1939), a student of the famous poet Mirzaboshi Komil, was a famous tanbur player. He perfectly mastered not only the art of tanbur playing, but also the art of calligraphy. Muhammad Yaqub Kharratov (Matyaqub Kharratov), a musician of the palace folk instrument ensemble led by the talented musician Komil Khorezmi, participated in the compilation of tanbur notation and the recording of Khorezm maqoms. Having received the Khorezm maqom series from his teacher, he made a great contribution to the preservation of the maqom. The creative and performing activity of the famous tanbur player and singer Niyozhoja Haji, who worked at the court of Muhammad Rahimkhan (1806-1825), took place in Khiva. He paid great attention to the Khorezm musical culture. According to Matyokub Kharratov, Niyozhoja went to Bukhara to study "Shashmaqom". After he returned from Bukhara, Bukhara maqoms were mastered by Khiva musicians and began to spread widely in Khorezm. Famous musicians of Khorezm, such as Mukhammadrahim Feruz, Kamil Khorezmiy, Mirzo Mukhammadrasul and others, in collaboration with Niyozhoja, enriched the maqoms by adding new instrumental sections. In the second half of the 19th century, the city of Kokand became a center where famous musicians gathered. Here, under the leadership of Master Khudoyberdi, a unique school was created to study the performing school of Uzbek folk instruments. Fergana instruments began to actively master the Bukhara shashmakom. Father - Jaloliddin Nosirov (1845-1928) was a maqom performer, a famous teacher, instrumentalist, master tanbur player. He first learned music from his mother, and then received education from his father, who was a brilliant connoisseur and skilled performer of maqoms. For many years, Ota-Jalol Nosirov was the permanent leader and singer of the Uzbek folk instrument ensemble at the palaces of Amir Olimkhan (Bukhara), Amir Muzaffarkhan (Shahrisabz), and Amir Otajonlar (Karmana, now Navoi). Ota G'iyos Abdugani (1858-1924) was a connoisseur of Uzbek music and a Bukhara tanbur player. He knew the Mushkulot part of Shashmaqom well and performed each maqom while preserving its unique style and characteristics. Hoji Abdulaziz Rasulev (1852-1936) was one of the famous performers of Uzbek and Tajik music, a student of the master tanbur player Hoji Rakhimkul. In 1888, he went to Bukhara. There, under the guidance of Ota Jaloliddin Nazirov, he mastered Shashmaqom perfectly in one year. A. Rasulov actively performed Uzbek folk music and maqoms in Fergana, Samarkand, and Tashkent. promoted.

They were all enlighteners, mentors of young musicians. Their pedagogical views and teachings are a new pedagogical vital source for performance on Uzbek folk instruments and are preserved as an immortal heritage.

After 1917, Uzbek musical art began to develop rapidly and energetically. Already in the first decade, certain achievements were achieved in the fields of music education, folklore studies, and performing arts. Great work was carried out in music educational institutions - the Turkestan People's Conservatory in Tashkent (1918) and its branches in Samarkand, Fergana (1919), and Bukhara (1920). They taught mainly Uzbek folk instruments and some European musical instruments (piano, violin, and percussion instruments). Although these musical educational institutions were not conservatories in the true sense of the word, they taught simple music theory and performing arts to those who did not have the opportunity to study the science of musical culture of the past. Thanks to this, amateur music spread widely in many cities of the young republic. The founder of Uzbek art, playwright, composer, teacher, and public figure Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy made a great contribution to the development of musical art. The traditions created by folk musicians and performers of the period before 1917 were embodied and continued in the work of the next generation of instrumentalists. Musicians-performers began to work in the reorganized cultural and educational organizations. The famous tanbur player and singer Shorahim Shoumarov in 1919 created a folk instrument ensemble at the "Namuna" boarding school in Tashkent. This ensemble later served as the basis for the organization of the Tashkent Music College. In the 1920s, musical groups such as "Ko'k ko'ylak", "San'atchi qizlar", and "Sanoyi nafisa" were formed at educational institutions, factories, and in rural areas. The organized creative groups included a flute player. There were also folk instrument ensembles with changchi, dutorchi, tanburchi, gijjakchi, doirachi, drummers and qashkar rubab musicians. Folk instrument ensembles were also formed in Fergana, Andijan, and Samarkand. They were led by famous instrumentalists Usta Olim Kamilov, Tokhtasin Jalilov, Ahmadjon Umirzokov, Yusufjon Shakarjonov, Usta Ro'zmat Isaboyev, Matyusuf Kharratov, Usta Toyir Marufjon Toshpulatov, and Muhiddin Mavlonov. Thanks to their fruitful work, many people enjoyed the art of performing on Uzbek folk instruments. In 1936, on the occasion of the decade in Moscow, Qori Yakubov was entrusted with the creation of the State Philharmonic, and he was appointed the first director of the philharmonic. Thanks to the determination of Qori Yakubov and other figures of musical art, a decision was made to establish the Tashkent State Conservatory. The creative activity of Yunus Rajabi (1897-1976), a successor of the traditions of Uzbek folk music, a master folk musician from Tashkent - dutor, tanbur, flute player, was characterized by broad musical and social features of enlightenment. The recording and preparation for publication of five volumes of Uzbek folk music was the most remarkable result of Yunus Rajabi's many years of creative activity. In 1927, Yunus Rajabiy organized a national ensemble of folk instruments under the Uzbek Radio Committee, consisting of 12 musicians (singers and musicians). He attracted to this ensemble musicians who were famous in Tashkent at that time - koshnaychi Khairulla Ubaydullaev, dutor players Abdusolat Vahobov, Orif Qosimov, tanbur players Rixsi Rajapov, Mahsudkhodja Yusupov, gijjak players Imamjon Ikromov, Nabi Hasanov, Mahmud Yusupov, flute players Dada Ali Soatkulov, Said Kalonov, khangchi players Nigmatjon Do'stmuhammedov, Fakhridin Sodiqov, Mahamatjon Rasulov, and doira player Dadakhodja Sottiyev. The ensemble's repertoire, along with Uzbek

folk tunes, included works by modern composers, including Yunus Rajabiy's "Chorgoh", "Ko'chabog'i", "Bayot", "Birlashingi", "Fabrika", "G'alaba", "Hammamiz", "Ilgor", "Mirzadavlat". Later, the ensemble included such famous singers of the republic as Mulla Tu'ychi Toshmuhamedov from Tashkent, domla Halim Ibodov from Bukhara, dutar player and singer Hoji Abdurakhmon Umarov from Samarkand, tanbur players and singers from Khorezm, Matyokub Kharratov, Safo Mugoniy, and Nazira Akhmedova from Tashkent. At the same time, the ensemble's performance repertoire expanded due to the musical and prose parts of "Shashmaqom": "Nasurullai", "Navru'zi Sabo", "Talqini ushak", "Sarvinozi talqincha", as well as such works by composers as "Uyg'oning", "Bizning qishloq", "Yashasin", "Kolkhozizim". In 1930, the Tashkent Higher Music School was opened, and in 1936, the first higher music institution in Central Asia - the Tashkent State Conservatory - was opened on its basis. The 1936-1937 academic year was a very important period for the development of musical education in the field of performance on folk instruments. It was during this period that, at the Tashkent Music School named after Hamza, on the initiative of AI Petrosyans, teachers such as Yu. Rajabiy, A. Daroshev, A. Mansurov, B. Gienko, N. Krestyanin, V. Marsinkovsky, A. Maksudov, O. Qosimov began to teach playing Uzbek folk instruments based on the generally accepted notation system. Sh. Shoakramov, A. Gofurov, M. Yunusov (chang), S. Yuldoshov, G. Qodirov (tanbur), A. Ilyosov, M. A'zamov, etc. were among their first students. such artists as Bukhara domla Halim Ibodov, Samarkand dutar player and singer Haji Abdurakhmon Umarov, Khorezm tanbur players and singers Matyokub Kharratov, Safo Mugoniy, and Nazira Akhmedova from Tashkent worked there. At this time, the ensemble's performance repertoire expanded to include the complex and prose parts of "Shashmaqom": "Nasurullai", "Navru'zi Sabo", "Talqini ushoq", "Sarvinozi talqincha", as well as works by composers such as "Uyg'oning", "Bizning qishloq", "Yashasin", "Kolkhozizim". In 1930, the Tashkent Higher Music School was opened, and in 1936, the first higher music school in Central Asia, the Tashkent State Conservatory, was opened on its basis. The 1936-1937 academic year was a very important period for the development of musical education in the field of performance on folk instruments. It was during this period that, at the Tashkent Music School named after Hamza, on the initiative of AI Petrosyans, teachers such as Yu. Rajabiy, A. Daroshev, A. Mansurov, B. Gienko, N. Krestyanin, V. Marsinkovsky, A. Maksudov, O. Qosimov began to teach playing Uzbek folk instruments based on the generally accepted notation system. Sh. Shoakramov, A. Gofurov, M. Yunusov (chang), S. Yuldoshov, G. Qodirov (tanbur), A. Ilyosov, M. A'zamov, etc. were among their first students. such artists as Bukhara domla Halim Ibodov, Samarkand dutar player and singer Haji Abdurakhmon Umarov, Khorezm tanbur players and singers Matyokub Kharratov, Safo Mugoniy, and Nazira Akhmedova from Tashkent worked there. At this time, the ensemble's performance repertoire expanded to include the complex and prose parts of "Shashmaqom": "Nasurullai", "Navru'zi Sabo", "Talqini ushoq", "Sarvinozi talqincha", as well as works by composers such as "Uyg'oning", "Bizning qishloq", "Yashasin", "Kolkhozizim". In 1930, the Tashkent Higher Music School was opened, and in 1936, the first higher music school in Central Asia, the Tashkent State Conservatory, was opened on its basis.

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Musical education and teachers The growth of the performing culture of Uzbek folk instruments, the mastery of the works of world classical composers, the active creative activity of Uzbek composers in creating special works for folk instruments became an important basis for the further development of the art of performing Uzbek folk instruments. At the same time, the issue of thorough and perfect training of highly qualified scientific, pedagogical and performing personnel was also put on the agenda. The development of performing Uzbek folk instruments in subsequent periods is closely connected with the activities of the Tashkent Conservatory. Since 1948, training in the performance of folk instruments began in higher musical institutions of our country, including the Tashkent State Conservatory named after M. Ashrafiy. AI Petrosyans headed the Department of Uzbek Folk Instruments (as part of the orchestra faculty), selected students, and drew up curricula. VAUspensky, MAAshrafiy, AIPetrosyans, IPBlagoveshchensky, BFGienko, GGSobitov played a major role in establishing professional education in the performance of Uzbek folk instruments at the Tashkent State Conservatory. In the first academic year of 1948-49, 13 musicians from the Uzbek State Philharmonic Orchestra of Folk Instruments were admitted to the conservatory. 10 of them: Nazir Nigmatov (koshnay), Abbas Bahromov, Alexander Evdokimov (primarubob), Lali Sultanova, Mirzaev, Buriboy Mirzaahmedov (kashkar), Mahamatjon Asilov, Obid Kholmukhamedov (gijjak), Anvar Liviev (doira) were admitted to the 1st year. Graduates of the Tashkent Music School named after Hamza Akhmadjon Odilov (chan), Valentina Borisenko (prima rubob), Feoktist Vasilev (kashkar rubob) were accepted into the 2nd year. Muhammadjon Mirzaev (born in 1913) is the most famous rubob player in the republic, a singer-composer. He graduated from the conservatory in the kashkar rubob class under the guidance of AI Petrosyans. Since 1951, in addition to working in the philharmonic orchestra, he has been mentoring young performers in studying the Uzbek folk musical heritage. In creative collaboration with People's Artists Kh.Mavlonova, M.Turgunbayeva, he created lyrical dance tunes such as "Bahor Valsi", "Yangi Tanovar", "Gulnoz", "Dilbar", "Gulhumor", "Dildor". Among the songs he created, "Shirmonoy", "Oltin sandiq", "Uch dugonalar" are especially popular. M. Mirzayev is a People's Artist of Uzbekistan, a member of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan and a laureate of several awards. He is considered one of the first rubab players to create the basis of an emotional and vivid style in rubab performance (later developed by young performers). Mirza Hakimovich Toirov (born in 1930). One of the first graduates of the Conservatory in the flute specialty (1956). Together with his teacher AI Petrosyans, he created the "Flute School" textbook. This manual made it possible to open flute classes in all music schools in Uzbekistan, as well as in neighboring republics. M. Toirov worked at the performance department since 1957, first as a teacher, then as an associate professor. At the same time, he also participated in the T. Jalilov Folk Instrument Orchestra. M. Toirov was a laureate of the All-Union Competition of Music Performers (1957) and the VI World Festival of Youth and Students (1957), participated in the Uzbek Art Decades held in Moscow, Estonia, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan. M. Toirov trained and brought up several talented flute players. So, based on the above, we can say that the national art of maqom, an integral part of the cultural heritage of our people, occupies an important place in our spiritual life with its ancient history, deep philosophical roots, unique artistic style, and rich creative traditions.

Currently, the resolution of the Head of our state dated November 17, 2017 “On measures for the further development of the Uzbek national maqom art” has become a historical document expressing high attention to our national art. Based on it, starting in 2018, the International Conference on Maqom Art will be held in the city of Shahrizabz every two years. On April 6, 2018, the next document of the President in this direction - the resolution “On holding the International Conference on Maqom Art” was adopted. The resolution of the Head of our state dated November 17, 2017 “On measures for the further development of the Uzbek national maqom art” has become a historical document expressing high attention to our national art. Based on it, starting in 2018, the International Conference on Maqom Art will be held in the city of Shahrizabz every two years. On April 6, 2018, the next document in this direction - the Resolution of our President "On holding the International Conference on Maqom Art" was adopted. Currently, our republic is working to establish international cooperation to widely promote the art of maqom and create non-traditional exhibitions.

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